

Reactions of 4-hydroxycoumarin with some α,β -unsaturated carbonyls and 1,3-dicarbonyls : trapping of 4-hydroxycoumarin tautomers; formation of a pimelic acid derivative and a novel bicyclo compound

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4-Hydroxycoumarin (1) being endowed with both nucleophilic and electrophilic properties furnishes the dimeric coumarin derivative 3 in a pyridine catalyzed self-condensation process; while its attempted morpholine catalyzed self-condensation yields no dimeric coumarin derivative, but leads to the formation of the enamine derivative 2, establishing the existence of the less stable 2,4-chromandione tautomer (1') of 4-hydroxycoumarin. Pyridine catalyzed condensation between 4-hydroxycoumarin and acrylic acid affords 4-salicyloylpimelic acid (4) via the formation of 3,3-disubstituted-4-hydroxycoumarin and its subsequent hydrolysis and decarboxylation. But the condensation under similar condition with crotonic acid and with mesityl oxide separately leads to the isolation of the pyranocoumarin derivatives 5 and 6, respectively, along with a little amount 3 in either case. However, when a β,β -disubstituted- α,β -unsaturated acid like β,β -dimethylacrylic acid, and α,β -unsaturated acids with a bulky β -substituent like cinnamic, *p*-chlorocinnamic and 3, 4-methylenedioxyacetic acids are used, no condensation product excepting the same dimeric coumarin derivative 3 is formed apparently due to the reduced electrophilicity of the β -carbon and steric crowding in the transition state. Condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin with ethyl acetoacetate produces the α -pyranocoumarin 7, while with acetylacetone leads to the formation of a novel bicyclo compound 8 having two 4-hydroxycoumarin moieties with one acetylacetone moiety bridging them. These condensations using other bases like sodium bicarbonate, piperidine and morpholine afford the same products with varied rates of their formation. Refluxing 4-hydroxycoumarin (1) or its enamine 2 with acetic anhydride in acetic acid gives 3-acetyl-2-hydroxy-4-chromanone (9), stabilized by intramolecular H-bonding and thus indicating the existence of the least stable tautomeric form 1'' (2-hydroxy-4-chromenone) of 4-hydroxycoumarin (1).

4-Hydroxycoumarin and its derivatives have been reported¹ to possess marked biological activities such as enzyme inhibition, hypotoxicity, carcinogenicity and anticoagulant and antibiotic action. Base-catalyzed condensation between 4-hydroxycoumarin and some α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and ketones was carried out in this laboratory earlier². By analogy, condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin (1) with some active methylene compounds and also with acetic anhydride was anticipated. During the present investigation, it was found that 4-hydroxycoumarin underwent self-condensation in the presence of pyridine, thereby establishing the presence of its tautomeric form 2,4-chromandione (1'). This tautomer was further trapped as its enamine when 4-hydroxycoumarin was refluxed with morpholine. 4-Hydroxycoumarin also underwent condensation with α,β -unsaturated carbonyls, obviously at 3-position through Michael type addition as expected, followed by another ring closure involving the OH group at 4-position and the free carbonyl in the adduct and in one case by subsequent cleavage of the coumarin

ring. In almost all cases a dimeric coumarin derivative 3 was also formed concomitantly, though in a small amount. β -Monosubstituted with a bulky group or β,β -disubstituted α,β -unsaturated acids did not condense at 3-position of 4-hydroxycoumarin as expected, from decreased electrophilicity and steric crowding consideration, and instead the self-condensation between two 4-hydroxycoumarin molecules leading to the dimeric product was observed. Condensation with active methylene compound like ethyl acetoacetate followed the expected course, while with acetylacetone an interesting bicyclo compound comprising two 4-hydroxycoumarin moieties and one acetylacetone moiety bridging them was isolated.

The possible transformations of the tautomeric forms [4-hydroxy-2-chromenone (= 4-hydroxycoumarin) (1), 2,4-chromandione (1') and 2-hydroxy-4-chromenone (1'')] of 4-hydroxycoumarin have been discussed and examined by different chemical methods³⁻⁶ and by NMR spectra and H-D exchange⁷. In the present study, the presence of the tauto-

meric forms 1' and 1'' of 4-hydroxycoumarin is gleaned from the formation of some reaction products discussed in the sequel. The ¹³C NMR spectra of 4-hydroxycoumarin and its derivatives, however, did not show⁸⁻¹⁰ the presence of the other tautomeric forms 1' and 1''.

enamine thus established the existence of 2,4-chromandione tautomeric form 1' of 4-hydroxycoumarin as the reactive intermediate and is rationalized mechanistically in Scheme 1. Since the 4-position of this tautomer can serve as an electrophilic centre, it is expected to undergo nucleophilic at-

Results and Discussion

The product obtained on refluxing a solution of 4-hydroxycoumarin (1) in morpholine for 8 h on chromatography over silica gel furnished the enamine 2, the structure of which was established through IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral evidence (*vide* experimental). The formation of this

Scheme 1. Probable pathway for the formation of 2.

Mechanism :

Scheme 2. Probable pathway for the formation of 3.

tack through C-3 of another molecule of 4-hydroxycoumarin in a base-catalyzed process.

Therefore, when 4-hydroxycoumarin was refluxed with pyridine for 12 h, the dimeric coumarin derivative 3 was isolated after proper work-up and chromatography. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR, and mass spectral analyses allowed us to confirm its structure unambiguously. A probable mechanism based upon the fact stated above is shown in Scheme 2. The formation of the dimer 3 also clearly establishes the existence of the tautomeric form 1' of 4-hydroxycoumarin.

The OH group at 4-position in the 4-hydroxy-2-chromenone form **1** activates the nucleophilic carbon at C-3 in the presence of a base and prompts it to react with a Michael type acceptor. Thus, 4-hydroxycoumarin upon refluxing with acrylic acid in the presence of pyridine for 8 h yielded 4-salicyloylpimelic acid (**4**), the structure of which was established through spectral studies (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR and MS). The absence of coumarin ring as evident from the spectral analyses emerges from the fact that 4-hydroxycoumarin underwent condensation with acrylic acid at C-3 twice and the 3,3-disubstituted derivative being an α,α -disubstituted- β -ketolactone readily cleaved subsequently to furnish **4**. The interesting feature of this molecule, in accordance with its ^1H NMR spectrum, is that it is an example of a simple achiral

Scheme 3. Probable pathway for the formation of **4**.

molecule having five adjacent prochiral centres and four enantiotopic pairs of two sets of constitutional heterotopic geminal hydrogens of which β and β' geminal hydrogens become diastereotopic due to restricted rotation. The probable pathway for its formation is depicted in Scheme 3. Here, despite the presence of the base pyridine, no dimeric coumarin derivative was formed presumably due to much faster rate of condensation than that of dimerization. Likewise, the condensation between 4-hydroxycoumarin and crotonic acid was accomplished by refluxing them together with pyridine for 12 h. The expected Michael addition was followed by cyclization involving the nucleophilic oxygen at C-4 and

electrophilic carboxyl carbon in the side-chain and 4-methyl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*]benzopyran-2,5-dione (**5**) was isolated after chromatographic purification. The structural elucidation was conventionally done through spectral studies (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, and MS). Here, the isolation of a little amount of the dimeric coumarin derivative **3** again establishes the tautomerism in 4-hydroxycoumarin. The formation of **5** is rationalized in Scheme 4.

Scheme 4. Probable pathway for the formation of **5**.

Similar condensation took place using mesityl oxide in place of acrylic acid or crotonic acid. The use of pyridine base, refluxing for 6 h and usual chromatographic separation and purification led to the isolation of the pyranocoumarin **6** along with the same dimeric coumarin derivative **3** in a small amount. However, mesityl oxide upon refluxing with 4-hydroxycoumarin for 48 h in presence of pyridine afforded **6** along with its isomer; but no dimeric product could be isolated. The pyranocoumarin was established as 2-hydroxy-2,4,4-trimethyl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*]benzopyran-5-one (**6**) from its spectral studies (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, and MS). The same dimeric coumarin derivative **3** was again obtained as the only product when 4-hydroxycoumarin was refluxed in pyridine for 12 h with each of β,β -dimethylacrylic acid, cinnamic acid, *p*-chlorocinnamic acid and 3,4-methylenedioxycinnamic acid. The fact that these acids failed to produce any condensation product may have its origin in the reduced electrophilic nature due to the electron-donating group at the β -carbon and/or the steric crowding at the β -carbon of the acids in the transition state which restricted the nucleophilic C-3 of 4-hydroxycoumarin to attack at β -position and condense with them. The probable pathway for the formation of **6** is shown in Scheme 5.

Condensation between 4-hydroxycoumarin and active methylene compounds was also achieved taking ethyl

Mechanism :

Scheme 5. Probable pathway for the formation of 6.

acetoacetate and acetylacetone. Pyridine base and a refluxing time of 8 and 3 h were employed, respectively. The reaction mixture was worked up usually and chromatographed over silica gel. The product was finally crystallized and characterized through spectral studies. In the case of ethyl acetoacetate, 4-methyl-2*H*,5*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*]benzopyran-2,5-dione (7) possessing a fused 2-chromenone ring was obtained, while with acetylacetone a novel bicyclo[3.3.1]nonane derivative 8 having two 4-hydroxycoumarin moieties bridged by one acetylacetone moiety was isolated. The structure of this bicyclo compound as elucidated from its spectral analyses possesses a C_2 symmetry passing through the methylene carbon in the bridge, which was further visualized from its 1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra and from the examination of its model. The plausible mechanisms for the formation of 7 and 8 are delineated in Schemes 6 and 7,

Mechanism :

Scheme 6. Probable pathway for the formation of 7.

respectively.

4-Hydroxycoumarin (1) or its enamine 2 when refluxed with acetic anhydride in acetic acid for 5 h produced 3-acetyl-2-hydroxy-4-chromenone (9). That this compound is not 3-

Mechanism :

Scheme 7. Probable pathway for the formation of 8.

acetyl-4-hydroxy-2-chromenone (10), was confirmed from careful 1H and ^{13}C NMR analyses¹¹. However, 1 upon treatment with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine formed its simple *O*-acetyl derivative¹². 4-Hydroxycoumarin upon treatment with Br_2 in gl. AcOH for 1 h was converted to its 3-bromo derivative 11 as a consequence of the expected electrophilic substitution by bromine at C-3. Compound 11 on acetylation with acetic anhydride in pyridine furnished its *O*-acetyl derivative 12.

Experimental

M.p.s. measured in open capillary tubes are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. 1H NMR (300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker-300 A spectrometer in $CDCl_3$ (unless mentioned otherwise); the TMS (δ 0.00) or solvent ($CHCl_3$ δ 7.26 and $CDCl_3$ δ 77.0) was used as the internal standard and *J* values are expressed in Hz. The mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV. The silica gel 60–120 mesh (Qualigens) and silica gel 230–400 mesh (SRL) were used for column chromatography and flash chromatography. Petrol refers to b.p. 60–80° fraction. The eluate fractions were monitored using microscopic slides with silica gel G layer put on them by dipping in its chloroform slurry, taking out and drying in ambient temperature; similar fractions were combined. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was used for drying organic extracts after reaction work-up.

Base-catalyzed reactions of 4-hydroxycoumarin :

Dimerization of 4-hydroxycoumarin : A solution of 4-

hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 500 mg) in pyridine (1 ml) was refluxed for 12 h. The reaction mixture was added to ice-cooled water (50 ml) acidified with HCl. The precipitated product was filtered; crystallization from petrol-acetone mixture afforded **3** (255 mg), m.p. 290°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3100 br (OH), 1700 (CO), 1600, 1550, 1500, 1450, 1380, 1200, 1150, 1100, 1050, 950, 860, 770 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (d_6 -DMSO) 7.91 (1H, d, J 7.2, H-5'), 7.66 (1H, t, J 7.5, H-7'), 7.57 (1H, t, J 7.5, H-8'), 7.40 (4H, m, H-5, H-6, H-7 and H-6'), 7.23 (1H, t, J 7.2, H-8), 6.43 (1H, s, H-3); δ_{C} (d_6 -DMSO) 163.94 (C-2'), 160.17 (C-2 and C-8'a), 153.54 (C-8a), 153.24 (C-4), 148.35 (C-4'), 132.80 (C-3 and C-7'), 131.77 (C-7), 126.70 (C-5), 124.20 (C-5), 123.90 (C-6), 119.44 (C-6'), 117.10 (C-8), 116.45 (C-4a), 116.38 (C-4'a); m/z (% rel. int.) 306 (M^+ , 45), 289 (40), 158 (32), 130 (15), 121 (100).

Formation of enamine 2 with morpholine : A solution of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 500 mg) in morpholine (2.5 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then dissolved in chloroform (20 ml) and chromatographed over silica gel, when petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate fractions afforded **2**, which was crystallized from petrol-acetone mixture as white needles (340 mg), m.p. 140°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3020, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1700 (CO), 1600, 1550, 1400, 1340, 1290, 1250, 1100, 1090, 1040, 930, 910, 880, 780 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.61–7.22 (4H, m, ArH's), 5.73 (1H, s, H-3), 3.93 (4H, t, J 4.5, H₂-2' and H₂-6'), 3.25 (4H, t, J 4.5, H₂-3' and H₂-5); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 162.30 (C-2), 161.0 (C-8a), 154.0 (C-4), 131.56 (C-7), 124.56 (C-6), 123.44 (C-5), 117.80 (C-8), 115.95 (C-4a), 98.0 (C-3), 66.30 (C-5' and C-3'), 51.4 (C-6' and C-2').

Condensation with acrylic acid : *Formation of 4* : A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (500 mg), acrylic acid (0.5 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) was refluxed for 8 h, during which the reaction mixture turned to red gummy mass. Ice-cooled water (20 ml) acidified with 6 *N* HCl was added to it. After 1 h, the reddish solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 $\times$ 50 ml). The extract was washed with water (2 $\times$ 50 ml), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , concentrated and finally chromatographed over silica gel. The petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluate fractions afforded γ -salicyloylpimelic acid (**4**), which was crystallized from petrol-acetone mixture in white needles (375 mg); m.p. 136°; positive NaHCO_3 test and soluble in 10% KOH giving a yellow solution on heating; $\nu_{\max}$ 2900 br (carboxylic OH), 2980, 1700 (CO), 1640, 1490, 1400, 1450, 1300, 1250, 1150, 1050, 960, 830, 800, 750 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (d_6 -DMSO) 7.89 (1H, d, J 7.8, H-6), 7.50 (1H, t, J 7, H-3), 6.92 (2H, t, J 8.1, H-5 and H-4), 3.67 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12.9, γ -H), 2.63 (4H, t, J 7.5, α -H₂'s and α' -H₂'s), 1.87 (2H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 19.8, two enantiotopic β and β' -

H's), 1.68 (2H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 13.5, other two enantiotopic β - and β' -H's); δ_{C} (d_6 -DMSO) 202.50 (CO), 173.90 (COOH), 161.20 (C-6'), 136.40 (C-4'), 130.60 (C-3'), 120.50 (C-1'), 119.35 (C-2'), 118.0 (C-5'), 44.0 (C-4), 31.30 (C-6 and C-2), 26.70 (C-5 and C-3); m/z (% rel. int.) 280 (M^+ , 10), 121 (100), 93 (12), 65 (18).

4-Methyl-3,4-dihydro-2H,5H-pyranof[3,2-c]benzopyran-2,5-dione (5) : A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 1 g), crotonic acid (1 g) and pyridine (1 ml) was refluxed for 12 h. The reaction mixture after usual work-up was chromatographed over silica gel. Petrol-ethyl acetate (19 : 1) eluate fractions furnished a white solid, which on crystallization from petrol-acetone afforded **5** (525 mg), m.p. 140°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3060 br, 1700 (CO), 1650, 1610, 1550, 1500, 1450, 1400, 1350, 1220, 1160, 1100, 1070, 1000, 750 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (d_6 -DMSO) 7.81 (1H, d, J 8, H-10), 7.52 (1H, d, J 7.8, H-7), 7.27 (2H, t, J 8, H-8 and H-9), 3.55 (1H, sextet, J 7, H-4), 2.72 (1H, dd, J 8.1, 7.5, H-3), 1.14 (3H, d, J 6.9, CH_3 at C-4); δ_{C} (d_6 -DMSO) 174.50 (C-2), 162.40 (C-5), 160.90 (C-6a), 152.50 (C-10b), 132.40 (C-8), 123.90 (C-10), 116.68 (C-7), 116.0 (C-10a), 108.88 (C-4a), 38.70 (C-4), 27.07 (C-3) and 18.58 (CH_3 at C-4); m/z (% rel. int.) 230 (M^+ , 30), 215 (30), 202 (60), 187 (100), 174 (30), 145 (15), 131 (25), 121 (80), 92 (85), 82 (18), 65 (15).

Moreover, the petrol-ethyl acetate (17 : 3) eluate fractions of the same chromatogram afforded **3** as an amorphous compound (320 mg), m.p. 290°.

Attempted condensation between 4-hydroxycoumarin and β,β -disubstituted or β -monosubstituted α,β -unsaturated acids : Attempts were made to condense 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**) separately with β,β -dimethylacrylic acid, cinnamic acid, *p*-chlorocinnamic acid and 3,4-methylenedioxycinnamic acid by usual refluxing for 12 h in the presence of pyridine (1 ml), which did not afford any expected condensation product. Instead, in every case the dimeric derivative **3** was isolated.

2-Hydroxy-2,4,4-trimethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H,5H-pyranof[3,2-c]benzopyran-5-one (6) : A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 500 mg), mesityl oxide (1 ml) and pyridine (3–4 drops) was refluxed for 6 h. Ice-cooled water (50 ml) acidified with HCl was added and the precipitate was extracted with ethyl acetate, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and chromatographed over silica gel. Petrol-ethyl acetate (19 : 1) eluate fractions gave **6**, which was crystallized from petrol-acetone (260 mg), m.p. 200°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3360 (OH), 2980 (C-H), 1680 (CO), 1630, 1570, 1500, 1450, 1350, 1300, 1280, 1260, 1220, 1160, 1150, 1080, 940, 880, 850, 810, 780 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (d_6 -DMSO) 7.78–7.30 (4H, m, ArH's), 7.06 (1H, s, exchange with D_2O , OH), 1.64

(2H, s, H-3), 1.40 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$ at C-4); δ_{C} 160.20 (C-5), 156.60 (C-10b), 152.06 (C-6a), 131.70 (C-8), 123.66 (C-9), 123.06 (C-10), 115.88 (C-10a), 115.80 (C-7 and C-4a), 108.36 (C-2), 98.72 (C-4), 47.52 (C-3), 30.30 (CH_3 at C-2), 28.34 and 26.33 ($2 \times \text{CH}_3$ at C-4).

4-Methyl-2H,5H-pyrano[3,2-c]benzopyran-5-one (7): 4-Hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 250 mg) along with ethyl acetoacetate (0.5 ml) and pyridine (4–6 drops) was refluxed for 8 h. Excess of ethyl acetoacetate and pyridine were removed by distillation and then the reaction mixture was chromatographed as usual. The petrol-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) eluate fractions furnished cotton-fibre crystals, which were further crystallized from petrol-chloroform mixture to get **7** (190 mg), m.p. 244°; ν_{max} 1710 (CO), 1620, 1540, 1480, 1450, 1390, 1350, 1260, 1190, 1150, 1090, 910, 900, 840, 760 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.10 (1H, dd, J 8, 1.2, H-10), 7.68 (1H, t, J 7, H-7), 7.40 (2H, m, H-9 and H-8), 6.20 (1H, d, J 1.2, =C-H allylic coupling, H-3), 2.64 (3H, s, CH_3 at C-4); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 162.0 (C-5), 157.70 (C-2), 155.90 (C-10b), 153.34 (C-6a), 134.58 (C-8), 125.0 (C-9), 124.0 (C-10), 116.90 (C-7), 114.29 (C-4a), 114.0 (C-3), 113.26 (C-10a), 22.45 (CH_3 at C-4); m/z (% rel. int.) 228 (M^+ , 50), 200 (100), 171 (25), 144 (25), 121 (10), 115 (15), 92 (30), 63 (20).

Condensation with acetylacetone : Formation of 8 : A mixture of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 1 g), acetylacetone (1.5 ml) and pyridine (6–8 drops) was refluxed for 3 h. The brown reaction mixture was then freed from excess acetylacetone and pyridine and extracted with chloroform. The extract was chromatographed over silica gel, when a white compound was obtained from petrol-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) mixture to get **8** which was crystallized from petrol-chloroform (815 mg), m.p. 255°; ν_{max} 1720 (CO), 1610, 1560, 1490, 1390, 1330, 1240, 1220, 1200, 1120, 1090, 1050, 1000, 900, 840, 800, 760 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.92 (2H, dd, J 7.8, 1.2, H-5 and H-5'), 7.52 (2H, m, J 7.5, 1.2, H-8 and H-8'), 7.23 (4H, m, H-6, H-7, H-6' and H-7'), 2.31 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.21 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 162.67 (C-2), 159.70 (C-4), 153.18 (C-8a), 133.0 (C-7), 124.19 (C-6), 124.07 (C-5), 116.29 (C-8), 114.77 (C-4a), 101.80 (C-3), 74.29 (qC), 44.19 (CH_2), 23.17 (CH_3); m/z (% rel. int.) 388 (M^+ , 35), 373 (25), 253 (18), 227 (20), 200 (100), 121 (70), 92 (20).

3-Acetyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-one (9) : 4-Hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 1 g) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (1 ml) in acetic acid (1 ml) for 5 h. The reaction mixture was chromatographed and petrol-ethyl acetate (10 : 1) eluate fractions afforded **9** (790 mg), m.p. 135°. The same method was repeated replacing 4-hydroxycoumarin by its enamine **2** with morpholine and the same compound **9** was ob-

tained : ν_{max} 1700 (CO), 1650, 1590, 1520, 1450, 1200, 1100, 1090, 1050, 1050, 1000, 900, 800, 750 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 14.28 (1H, s, exchange with D_2O , chelated-OH), 8.81 (1H, d, J 8.7, H-5), 8.36 (1H, d, J 7.4, H-8), 7.65 (1H, t, J 7.8, H-7), 7.48 (1H, t, J 7.5, H-6), 2.62 (3H, s, COCH_3); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 205.90 (COCH_3), 178.70 (C-4), 158.90 (C-2), 154.85 (C-4a), 136.0 (C-8a), 125.84 (C-7), 124.38 (C-6), 117.0 (C-5), 115.30 (C-8), 101.48 (C-3), 29.80 (COCH_3).

3-Bromo-4-hydroxycoumarin (11) : To a solution of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 1 g) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml), bromine (0.3 ml) was added dropwise with stirring in 1 h. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ice-cold water (20 ml) and the precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and dried. It was then chromatographed over silica gel; the petrol-ethyl acetate eluate fractions afforded **3**, crystallizing from acetone-chloroform as off-white needles (835 mg), m.p. 190°; ν_{max} 3185 (OH), 1700 (CO), 1608, 1551, 1209, 997, 746 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (d_6 -DMSO) 7.87 (1H, d, J 8.7, H-5), 7.61 (1H, t, J 8, 8.3, H-6 and H-7), 7.33 (1H, t, J 7.5, 2, H-8); δ_{C} (d_6 -DMSO) 162.83 (C-2), 158.74 (C-4), 151.73 (C-5a), 132.84 (C-7), 124.45 (C-6), 123.51 (C-5), 116.42 (C-8), 116.17 (C-4a), 88.88 (C-3).

3-Bromo-4-acetoxycoumarin (12) : Few drops of pyridine was added with stirring to a solution of 3-bromo-4-hydroxycoumarin (**11**; 1 g) in minimum volume (1 ml) of acetic anhydride. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. After usual work-up and chromatography over silica gel the petrol-ethyl acetate eluate fractions afforded **12** (850 mg), m.p. 190°; ν_{max} 1783, 1725, 1611, 1561, 1439, 1353, 1278, 1167, 1085, 989, 899 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.62 (1H, ddd, J 8.7, 8.6, 3, H-6), 7.51 (1H, dd, J 9, 8.9, H-7), 7.39 (1H, d, J 8.4, 7.8, H-5), 7.34 (1H, t, J 7.8, 7.8, 3, H-8), 2.51 (3H, s, OCOCH_3); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 201.01 (OCOCH_3), 165.21 (C-2), 157.64 (C-4), 152.02 (C-5a), 132.95 (C-7), 124.90 (C-6), 122.73 (C-5), 116.99 (C-8), 116.27 (C-4a), 104.99 (C-3), 20.48 (COCH_3).

4-O-Acetylcoumarin : 4-Hydroxycoumarin (**1**; 100 mg) was kept overnight at RT with acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) and pyridine (1–2 drops). Usual work-up followed by crystallization from chloroform-methanol yielded the acetyl derivative in fine colourless needles (75 mg), m.p. 102°; ν_{max} 1768 (CO), 1728, 1608, 1373, 1197, 1080, 907, 758 cm^{-1} .

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